

Strengthening reading comprehension through affective communication and artificial intelligence with validation by neutrosophic numbers

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Abstract. This investigation explores whether emotional communication empowered by artificial intelligence tools is needed for pedagogical integration for reading comprehension for Third Graders at Santiago Fernández García Educational Unit. Through Teacher interviews, classroom observations and pedagogical assessments, the investigator uncovered methodological insufficiencies that not only hinder the literal aspects of reading comprehension but also interpretative and critical aspects. Teachers hold a fortuitous upper hand regarding these advancements; however, test results show non-sufficient didactic planning geared toward emotional awareness strategy developments through artificial intelligence. Suggested artificial intelligence developments in this area show to be text generators or emotional detectors; however, this is only relative for emotional, motivational, empathic awareness and reading guidance. Thus, the investigator deduces that extensive use of empowered emotional communication through resources of artificial intelligence in a pedagogical setting not only cares for pedagogical bonds but is a necessity for compassionate readers and critical assessors. All strategies are justified with neutrosophic number assessments based upon uncertainties of methodological learning strategy approach.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension, Artificial Intelligence, Affective Communication, Pedagogical Strategies, Motivation, Teacher-Student Interaction, Neutrosophic Numbers.

1. Introduction

Communication represents a structuring process within the educational process; it not only allows the transmission of knowledge, but also builds bonds, meanings, and shared senses among those who participate in the pedagogical act. In the school environment, communication goes beyond issuing messages or instructions; it is about generating an interaction where language, gestures, emotions, and listening become vehicles for the collective construction of knowledge. From this perspective, affective communication, enhanced by artificial intelligence tools, emerges as an essential pedagogical tool, since it enables the creation of empathetic, safe, and stimulating environments that favor learning in all its dimensions [2], [22].

In the reading process, this communicative dimension acquires particular relevance. Reading, understood as a cultural and cognitive practice, requires the reader's active participation in the interpretation of the text; however, for this interpretation to be profound, the student needs to feel emotionally connected to what they read. According to [3], understanding a text is not only about decoding it, but also about inhabiting it through experience, connecting with its ideas, and formulating

new readings that involve the reader's subjectivity. In this sense, the quality of the bond between teacher and student, enriched by the use of artificial intelligence to personalize reading experiences or analyze emotional dynamics, directly influences the disposition toward reading; a relationship mediated by affectivity and supported by technology generates an environment where reading is not perceived as an obligation, but as an opportunity to explore, imagine, and understand the world.

At the basic education level, particularly in third grade, students go through a stage of cognitive, emotional, and social transformation; their interpretive abilities are still being consolidated, while they face academic demands that require greater autonomy. This situation demands pedagogical practices that consider not only academic content but also the student's emotional state, their perception of the school environment, and their connection to the learning process, supported by artificial intelligence tools that optimize teaching. The educational experience cannot be dissociated from the emotional experience that permeates it; what the student feels when reading influences what they understand.

At the Santiago Fernández García Educational Unit, limited reading comprehension performance has been identified among third-year elementary school students. At this age, children are at an early stage of acquiring reading skills, and are expected to identify main ideas, recognize characters and settings, and establish basic relationships between elements of the text. However, many students have been observed to struggle with these tasks, demonstrating a poor ability to interpret what they read, poor information retention, and a limited connection between the text and their personal experiences.

These difficulties cannot be attributed solely to technical or methodological factors. Academic communication has been found to focus on completing activities, without considering the emotional dimension or the potential of artificial intelligence as mediators of learning. Interaction between teachers and students lacks emotional and technological elements that foster motivation, confidence, and interest in reading, fundamental aspects at this stage of development.

The absence of pedagogical strategies that integrate affective communication and artificial intelligence limits the establishment of a positive connection with the reading process, affecting students' willingness to actively participate in reading activities. In this context, there is a need to investigate the impact of affective communication, combined with artificial intelligence tools, as a pedagogical strategy on the development of third-grade students' reading comprehension, recognizing that emotional and technological components are key to the comprehensive development of learning in childhood. This situation has led to the formulation of the following scientific problem: How does affective communication, supported by artificial intelligence, influence the development of reading comprehension among third-grade students at the Santiago Fernández García Educational Unit?

The main objective of this research is to propose didactic strategies based on affective communication and artificial intelligence to strengthen the learning of reading comprehension in third-year students of Basic General Education, integrating innovative pedagogical techniques with an emotional and technological approach adapted to their level of development, in order to significantly improve their reading skills. The validation of these strategies is carried out through neutrosophic numbers [32], [33], [34], [35], [36], which allow evaluating their effectiveness considering the uncertainty inherent in the educational context.

2. Preliminaries.

2.1. Communication in the educational process

Communication constitutes a structural component of the educational process, as it articulates the interaction between teachers and students; it is through this process that information is shared, learning is generated, and bonds are built. According to [20], communicating in the classroom involves not only emitting content, but also understanding the codes, silences, gestures, and feelings that circulate in that symbolic space. In this sense, it is considered that academic communication must integrate verbal and

nonverbal, rational and emotional, explicit and implicit dimensions to achieve comprehensive educational interaction.

Several studies have shown that effective classroom communication fosters environments that encourage critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and active participation [10], [4]. Furthermore, a teacher's ability to adapt their language, expressions, and attitude influences students' willingness to engage in learning. Communication, therefore, is not limited to transmitting content; it constitutes a means of shaping attitudes, developing social skills, and generating confidence in the learning process.

2.2. Affective communication and its influence on learning

Affective communication, in this context, refers to the educator's ability to establish empathic relationships with their students; these relationships are based on trust, active listening, respect, and emotional validation. According to [13], a teacher's emotional intelligence is crucial for generating classroom climates that stimulate motivation, self-regulation, and an interest in learning. This form of communication fosters an environment where mistakes are not penalized but rather reinterpreted as an opportunity for growth.

Studies such as [9] show that students exposed to emotionally positive interactions develop greater participation, improve their academic performance and reinforce their social skills. [21] argue that the emotional bond between the educator and the student acts as a mediator between the pedagogical experience and cognitive achievements. Affectivity in communication allows the student to feel understood; this directly influences their openness to take on intellectual challenges, such as interpretive reading or critical analysis.

2.3. Reading comprehension and emotional bonding

Reading comprehension cannot be approached as an exclusively technical process. It involves decoding, yes, but also interpreting, inferring, connecting, and reflecting; linguistic, cultural, and emotional factors intervene in this process. [3] points out that the act of reading is a social practice that demands active and personal involvement from the reader. For this reason, students who feel emotionally disconnected from the text or the pedagogical environment have greater difficulty accessing deeper levels of comprehension.

[16] argue that interest in reading and emotional engagement with texts are predictors of reading success. That is, when students establish an emotional relationship with what they read—whether through identification with the characters, connection to their experiences, or intellectual curiosity—they achieve higher levels of interpretation. Consequently, the teacher's affective communication influences the way in which the student positions himself before the text; the tone, attitude, and disposition of the educator shape the way in which the student assumes the reading experience.

2.4. Pedagogical strategies and emotional communication

Methodologies that integrate affective communication into their didactic design allow reading instruction to be transformed into a meaningful experience. [15] identify that the most effective strategies for improving reading comprehension are those that combine explicit instruction with emotionally enriched classroom environments. These strategies include shared reading, modeling reading thinking, literary dialogue, and connecting the text with personal experience.

On the other hand, authors such as [26] emphasize that teaching reading not only involves teaching how to identify information, but also how to construct meaning; to achieve this, it is essential that the student feels that his or her subjective experience takes place within the classroom. In this sense, the role of the teacher as an affective mediator is essential; his or her ability to generate open questions,

promote emotional expression in relation to the text, and recognize the student's interpretations transforms reading into a social and reflective practice.

2.5. Emotional education and reading training

Emotional education is conceived as a process that enhances the development of personal skills to identify, understand, and regulate one's own and others' emotions. [1] suggests that these skills should be integrated transversally into the curriculum, especially in areas such as reading, where emotions act as activators of comprehension and memory. Consequently, programs that promote reading should consider not only the difficulty levels of the text, but also the degree of emotional involvement that these can generate in students.

Integrating emotional communication into reading education implies understanding that reading is also feeling; when the reader is moved by the text, they generate a meaningful memory, internalize it, and transform it. This relationship between emotion and cognition has been extensively documented by authors such as [37], who maintain that emotions are a constitutive part of all complex learning; therefore, the design of reading strategies must incorporate spaces for emotional reflection, empathic dialogue, and the appreciation of the reading experience as a personal and collective experience.

2.6. The classroom climate as a factor of pedagogical mediation

The classroom climate is shaped by the relationships established between its members; it depends not only on the rules or the organization of the physical space, but also—and especially—on the quality of communicative interaction. An affective and respectful environment promotes a sense of belonging, reduces levels of academic anxiety, and encourages active student participation. According to [38], a favorable school climate is associated with increased academic performance and the development of metacognitive skills, since students perceive the classroom as a safe space to express ideas and emotions.

In this context, affective communication is not limited to individual teacher-student interaction; it contributes to the creation of a school culture that values empathy, listening, and mutual recognition. [39] argue that a positive emotional climate creates favorable conditions for autonomous and collaborative learning, while fostering emotional self-regulation and a disposition toward critical reading. Thus, building an appropriate pedagogical climate becomes an indirect strategy for improving reading comprehension and strengthening the connection with the content.

2.7. Reading motivation and its relationship with affectivity

Reading motivation is directly linked to the value students assign to reading and their expectation of success when confronted with a text. This motivation does not arise spontaneously; it is built through positive reading experiences, accompanied by emotional recognition and empathic feedback. [16] assert that students motivated to read are those who find personal meaning in texts and perceive reading as a pleasurable and useful activity.

In this sense, the teacher's communicative style decisively influences the construction of this motivation; when the educator validates the student's emotions regarding the texts, recognizes their interpretations, and creates an environment of respect, it contributes to awakening the desire to read. Furthermore, reading motivation is closely linked to self-reflection; if the student feels that their perspective is valued, they will be more willing to explore, question, and delve deeper into their reading, which enriches their understanding and critical analysis [12].

2.8. Artificial Intelligence in Education and its Impact on Reading Comprehension

2.8.1. Introduction to the Role of Artificial Intelligence in Education

Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative tool in the educational field, redefining teaching and learning processes by offering personalized, interactive, and data-driven solutions. In the context of the educational process, communication, understood as a structuring pillar, not only allows the transmission of knowledge, but also builds links and shared meanings [2], [22]. AI enhances this dynamic by facilitating more dynamic and adapted interactions, supporting both teachers and students in creating stimulating learning environments. In particular, AI stands out for its ability to analyze large volumes of data, identify learning patterns, and offer personalized resources, which is especially valuable in basic education, where students, such as third-graders, go through critical stages of cognitive, emotional, and social development.

The integration of AI in education goes beyond the simple automation of tasks; it allows for the design of learning experiences that respond to the individual needs of students, fostering motivation and active participation. In the case of reading comprehension, AI not only supports the decoding of texts, but also facilitates the emotional connection with the content, a crucial aspect for students, according to [3], to "inhabit" the texts from their personal experience. This chapter explores how AI, in synergy with affective communication, can strengthen reading comprehension in third-grade students, addressing their specific challenges and enhancing the emotional bonds that enrich the reading process. The validation of these strategies is carried out through neutrosophic numbers [32]–[36], which allow evaluating their effectiveness under the uncertainty inherent in the educational context.

2.8.2. Artificial Intelligence as a Pedagogical Tool

Personalization of Learning

AI offers adaptive learning systems that adjust educational content according to the needs, rhythms, and learning styles of each student. In basic education, where third-grade students present a wide diversity in their reading skills, AI can recommend texts with appropriate levels of difficulty, integrating elements that arouse emotional interest. For example, AI-based platforms, such as reading recommendation systems, analyze students' reading history and emotional preferences to suggest texts that connect with their experiences, aligning with the idea [3] that deep comprehension requires subjective involvement. These tools, by personalizing the reading experience, reinforce motivation and disposition towards reading, complementing the teacher's affective communication.

Emotional Analysis and Real-Time Feedback

AI also enables emotion analysis through technologies such as facial recognition or natural language processing. In the classroom, these tools can identify students' emotional states during reading activities, allowing teachers to adjust their approach to foster an empathetic and safe environment, as proposed by [2] and [22]. For example, an AI system can detect if a student is showing frustration when reading a complex text and suggest affective strategies, such as a group discussion or an expressive activity, to reconnect the student with the content. This real-time feedback strengthens the teacher-student bond, a key factor for meaningful learning.

Task Automation and Teaching Support

AI not only benefits students but also eases the burden on teachers by automating tasks such as assessing open-ended responses or generating personalized activities. In the context of reading

comprehension, AI tools can analyze students' responses to questions about texts, identifying patterns at the levels of literal, inferential, and critical comprehension. This allows teachers to design targeted interventions, such as the strategies proposed in the original article ("I read and tell you with emotion" or "Reading with friends"), that integrate affectivity with technological support. By freeing up time, AI allows teachers to focus on emotional interaction, reinforcing the learning environment described by [2].

2.8.3. Specific Applications of AI in Reading Comprehension

Text Recommendation Systems

In the third-grade context, where students are consolidating basic reading skills, AI-based text recommendation systems can select materials that balance cognitive challenge with emotional interest. For example, an algorithm can analyze a student's vocabulary level, syntactic complexity, and thematic preferences to suggest stories or tales that connect with their personal experiences, as highlighted in the "Stories from the Heart" strategy. This personalization fosters motivation and an emotional connection with the text, a crucial aspect for reading to be perceived as an opportunity for exploration, according to [3].

Comprehension Analysis Tools

AI can assess reading comprehension by analyzing written or oral responses to questions about texts. Natural language processing algorithms can classify responses into levels of comprehension (literal, inferential, critical), identifying areas of difficulty. For example, if a student struggles to infer implicit information, as observed in the original article (60% difficulty interpreting figurative language), AI can suggest specific activities, such as emotional association exercises or guided questions, that complement the teacher's affective communication. These tools enhance proposed strategies, such as "The Circle of Heard Words," by offering accurate and personalized feedback.

Gamification and Interactive Environments

Gamification, supported by AI, transforms reading into an interactive and motivating experience. Educational platforms using AI can create reading games where students solve text-based puzzles, identify characters' emotions, or reconstruct stories, as in the "Emotional Text" strategy. These activities, designed with playful and emotional elements, reinforce active participation and enjoyment of reading, aligning with [22]'s principle that a safe and stimulating environment fosters learning. In third grade, where motivation is key, AI can adapt the difficulty levels of games to maintain interest without generating frustration.

Chatbots and Emotional Dialogue

chatbots can act as mediators in reading activities, guiding students through open-ended questions that stimulate emotional reflection. For example, a chatbot can ask a student how they felt while reading a story or what a situation in the text reminded them of, fostering the personal connection described by [3]. In the classroom, these chatbots complement the teacher's affective communication, allowing for individualized interactions even in large groups. In the "Reading with Friends" strategy, a chatbot can moderate virtual group discussions, ensuring that all students actively participate.

Synergy between Affective Communication and Artificial Intelligence

Affective communication, as described in the original article, is a cornerstone of creating empathetic environments that motivate students to read. AI enhances this dimension by offering tools that personalize the reading experience and analyze the emotional dynamics of the classroom. For example, the "I read to you and tell you with emotion" strategy can be integrated with an AI system that analyzes students' facial expressions during reading aloud, identifying emotions such as interest or confusion. This information allows teachers to adjust their tone or incorporate additional affective dynamics, strengthening the emotional bond described by [2].

Furthermore, AI can facilitate the implementation of collaborative strategies, such as "Reading with Friends," by managing virtual groups or discussion platforms that promote mutual respect and validation. By combining teacher empathy with technological precision, an environment is created where students not only understand texts, but also experience them as meaningful experiences, in line with the vision of [3]. This synergy addresses the limitations identified in the article, such as the lack of emotional connection with the texts, by integrating technology in a way that reinforces, not replaces, human interaction.

3. Methodology.

This study adopts a mixed-method approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques. The choice of this approach is justified by the need to obtain a holistic perspective on the impact of affective communication on third-grade students' reading comprehension. The mixed-method approach allows combining objective (quantitative) and subjective (qualitative) data, providing a more complete and robust understanding of the phenomenon studied. According to [6], this approach is ideal for addressing the complexity of the topic from multiple perspectives, enriching the study's findings and conclusions.

Types of research

- Descriptive: Used to document and characterize the use of affective communication in the educational context and its relationship with reading comprehension. This type of research provides an accurate view of the observed phenomena without directly intervening in the process ([17]).
- Explanatory: Facilitates the identification of causal correlations between the implementation of affective communication and the improvement of reading comprehension. This approach is crucial to understanding the dynamics between the variables under study ([24]).
- Classroom action research: Involves educators in a process of continuous improvement within the classroom. This method allows teachers to implement, reflect on, and adjust affective communication strategies in real time, promoting collaborative and reflective problem-solving in education ([18]).

Research methods and techniques

Theoretical methods:

- Analysis-synthesis method. This method will be used to search for the foundations and causes, which will be analyzed and synthesized to support the research. The results of the investigative process will also be summarized during the diagnostic and validation phases.
- Inductive-deductive method: Applied to observe and analyze possible solutions, evaluating the influence of affective communication on the teacher-student relationship

and its impact on academic performance. This method allows for the identification of patterns and trends that contribute to more meaningful student learning.

- **Systems Approach:** Allows a comprehensive view of the phenomenon studied, considering the interrelationships between the different components of the educational process.

Empirical methods:

- Interviews with teachers and observations of third-grade language and literature classes were conducted to gather information that would allow for the identification of the causes that have led to reading comprehension limitations among third-grade students.
- Pedagogical test for students to diagnose the reading comprehension of third-grade students with the purpose of seeking information that allows the identification of the reading comprehension levels of third-year students of Basic General Education.
- Consultation with specialists and recording of experiences were used in the process of validating the proposed solution to the scientific problem.

The mathematical statistical method, taking into account percentage calculations, is a fundamental procedure for analyzing the data obtained and evaluating the effectiveness of the pedagogical strategies implemented.

The sampling used in this research is intentionally non-probabilistic, with participants deliberately selected based on specific criteria relevant to the study. For the teacher interviews and classroom observations, the sample consisted of 25 Basic General Education (EGB) teachers, from whom a sample of 7 middle school teachers was selected, representing 28% of the total population. Regarding the pedagogical test, the sample included 72 third-year students, from whom a sample of 25 students was selected, representing 34.7% of the total population. This approach provides detailed and specific information on pedagogical practices and reading comprehension levels, facilitating the evaluation of the impact of the implemented affective communication strategies.

Specific indicators will be used to evaluate the effectiveness of affective communication strategies in improving reading comprehension, such as the level of student engagement, the quality of classroom interactions, and the results of pedagogical tests.

The research unfolds in three phases: first, the causal diagnosis of the problem; second, the development of teaching strategies for developing reading comprehension through effective communication; and third, the validation of the proposal.

Neutrosophic Z numbers for validation

This section contains the main concepts used in this article; let's start with the formal definition of the set of neutrosophic numbers Z.

Definition 1 ([32-36]). Let X be a set of universes. A *neutrosophic number* Z The set in X is defined as follows:

$$S_Z = \{ \langle x, T(V, R)(x), I(V, R)(x), F(V, R)(x) \rangle : x \in X \} \quad (1)$$

Where $T(V, R)(x) = (T_V(x), T_R(x))$, $I(V, R)(x) = (I_V(x), I_R(x))$, $F(V, R)(x) = (F_V(x), F_R(x))$ are functions from X to $[0, 1]^2$, which are the ordered pairs of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity, respectively. The first component V is the neutrosophic values at X , and the second component R is the neutrosophic reliability measures for V , satisfying the conditions $0 \leq T_V(x) + I_V(x) + F_V(x) \leq 3$ and $0 \leq T_R(x) + I_R(x) + F_R(x) \leq 3$.

For convenience, we denote it $\langle x, T(V, R)(x), I(V, R)(x), F(V, R)(x) \rangle$ as $S_Z = \langle T(V, R), I(V, R), F(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_V, T_R), (I_V, I_R), (F_V, F_R) \rangle$ what is called NZN.

Definition 2 ([32-36]). Let $S_{Z_1} = \langle T_1(V, R), I_1(V, R), F_1(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_{V_1}, T_{R_1}), (I_{V_1}, I_{R_1}), (F_{V_1}, F_{R_1}) \rangle$ and $S_{Z_2} = \langle T_2(V, R), I_2(V, R), F_2(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_{V_2}, T_{R_2}), (I_{V_2}, I_{R_2}), (F_{V_2}, F_{R_2}) \rangle$. Let NZN and be two $\lambda > 0$. Then, we get the following relationships:

1. $S_{Z_2} \subseteq S_{Z_1} \Leftrightarrow T_{V_2} \leq T_{V_1}, T_{R_2} \leq T_{R_1}, I_{V_1} \leq I_{V_2}, I_{R_1} \leq I_{R_2}, F_{V_1} \leq F_{V_2}, F_{R_1} \leq F_{R_2}$,
2. $S_{Z_1} = S_{Z_2} \Leftrightarrow S_{Z_2} \subseteq S_{Z_1}$ and $S_{Z_1} \subseteq S_{Z_2}$,
3. $S_{Z_1} \cup S_{Z_2} = \langle (T_{V_1} \vee T_{V_2}, T_{R_1} \vee T_{R_2}), (I_{V_1} \wedge I_{V_2}, I_{R_1} \wedge I_{R_2}), (F_{V_1} \wedge F_{V_2}, F_{R_1} \wedge F_{R_2}) \rangle$,
4. $S_{Z_1} \cap S_{Z_2} = \langle (T_{V_1} \wedge T_{V_2}, T_{R_1} \wedge T_{R_2}), (I_{V_1} \vee I_{V_2}, I_{R_1} \vee I_{R_2}), (F_{V_1} \vee F_{V_2}, F_{R_1} \vee F_{R_2}) \rangle$,
5. $(S_{Z_1})^c = \langle (F_{V_1}, F_{R_1}), (1 - I_{V_1}, 1 - I_{R_1}), (T_{V_1}, T_{R_1}) \rangle$,
6. $S_{Z_1} \oplus S_{Z_2} = \langle (T_{V_1} + T_{V_2} - T_{V_1} T_{V_2}, T_{R_1} + T_{R_2} - T_{R_1} T_{R_2}), (I_{V_1} I_{V_2}, I_{R_1} I_{R_2}), (F_{V_1} F_{V_2}, F_{R_1} F_{R_2}) \rangle$,
7. $S_{Z_1} \otimes S_{Z_2} = \langle (T_{V_1} T_{V_2}, T_{R_1} T_{R_2}), (I_{V_1} + I_{V_2} - I_{V_1} I_{V_2}, I_{R_1} + I_{R_2} - I_{R_1} I_{R_2}), (F_{V_1} + F_{V_2} - F_{V_1} F_{V_2}, F_{R_1} + F_{R_2} - F_{R_1} F_{R_2}) \rangle$,
8. $\lambda S_{Z_1} = \langle (1 - (1 - T_{V_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - T_{R_1})^\lambda), (I_{V_1}^\lambda, I_{R_1}^\lambda), (F_{V_1}^\lambda, F_{R_1}^\lambda) \rangle$,
9. $S_{Z_1}^\lambda = \langle (T_{V_1}^\lambda, T_{R_1}^\lambda), (1 - (1 - I_{V_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - I_{R_1})^\lambda), (1 - (1 - F_{V_1})^\lambda, 1 - (1 - F_{R_1})^\lambda) \rangle$.

To compare two NZNs that have $S_{Z_i} = \langle T_i(V, R), I_i(V, R), F_i(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_{V_i}, T_{R_i}), (I_{V_i}, I_{R_i}), (F_{V_i}, F_{R_i}) \rangle (i = 1, 2)$, we have the scoring function:

$$Y(S_{Z_i}) = \frac{2 + T_{V_i} T_{R_i} - I_{V_i} I_{R_i} - F_{V_i} F_{R_i}}{3} \quad (2)$$

Note that $Y(S_{Z_i}) \in [0, 1]$. Therefore, $Y(S_{Z_2}) \leq Y(S_{Z_1})$ implies $S_{Z_2} \preceq S_{Z_1}$.

Let's illustrate equation 2 with an example.

Example 1. Let $S_{Z_1} = \langle (0.9, 0.8), (0.1, 0.9), (0.2, 0.9) \rangle$, then we have $Y(S_{Z_1}) = \frac{2 + (0.9)(0.8) - (0.1)(0.9) - (0.2)(0.9)}{3} = 0.81666$.

Definition 3 ([32-36]). Sea $S_{Z_i} = \langle T_i(V, R), I_i(V, R), F_i(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_{V_i}, T_{R_i}), (I_{V_i}, I_{R_i}), (F_{V_i}, F_{R_i}) \rangle (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ be a set of NZN and NZNWAA is a map from $[0, 1]^n$ into $[0, 1]$, such that the operator NZNWAA is defined as follows:

$$NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i S_{Z_i} \quad (3)$$

Where is $\lambda_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ the weight of S_{Z_i} satisfying $0 \leq \lambda_i \leq 1$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1$.

Thus, the NZNWAA formula is calculated as:

$$NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) = \langle (1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - T_{V_i})^{\lambda_i}, 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - T_{R_i})^{\lambda_i}), (\prod_{i=1}^n I_{V_i}^{\lambda_i}, \prod_{i=1}^n I_{R_i}^{\lambda_i}), (\prod_{i=1}^n F_{V_i}^{\lambda_i}, \prod_{i=1}^n F_{R_i}^{\lambda_i}) \rangle \quad (4)$$

NZNWAA satisfies the following properties:

1. Is an NZN,
2. It is idempotent $NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_1}, \dots, S_{Z_1}) = S_{Z_1}$,
3. Note, $\min\{S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}\} \leq NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) \leq \max\{S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}\}$,
4. Monotony, if $\forall i S_{Z_i} \preceq S_{Z_i}^*$ then $NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) \preceq NZNWAA(S_{Z_1}^*, S_{Z_2}^*, \dots, S_{Z_n}^*)$.

Definition 4 ([32-36]). Sea $S_{Z_i} = \langle T_i(V, R), I_i(V, R), F_i(V, R) \rangle = \langle (T_{V_i}, T_{R_i}), (I_{V_i}, I_{R_i}), (F_{V_i}, F_{R_i}) \rangle (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ be a set of NZN and NZNWGA be a map from $[0, 1]^n$ into $[0, 1]$, such that the operator NZNWGA is defined as follows:

$$NZNWGA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) = \sum_{i=1}^n S_{Z_i}^{\lambda_i} \quad (5)$$

Where is $\lambda_i (i = 1, 2, \dots, n)$ the weight of S_{Z_i} satisfying $0 \leq \lambda_i \leq 1$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = 1$.

Therefore, the NZNWGA formula is calculated as:

$$NZNWGA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) = \langle (\prod_{i=1}^n T_{V_i}^{\lambda_i}, \prod_{i=1}^n T_{R_i}^{\lambda_i}), (1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - I_{V_i})^{\lambda_i}, 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - I_{R_i})^{\lambda_i}), (1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - F_{V_i})^{\lambda_i}, 1 - \prod_{i=1}^n (1 - F_{R_i})^{\lambda_i}) \rangle \quad (6)$$

NZNWGA satisfies the following properties:

1. Is an NZN,
2. It is idempotent $NZNWGA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_1}, \dots, S_{Z_1}) = S_{Z_1}$,
3. Note, $\min\{S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}\} \leq NZNWGA(S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}) \leq \max\{S_{Z_1}, S_{Z_2}, \dots, S_{Z_n}\}$,

4. Monotony, if $\forall i S_{z_i} \leq S_{z_i}^*$ then $NZNWGA(S_{z_1}, S_{z_2}, \dots, S_{z_n}) \leq NZNWGA(S_{z_1}^*, S_{z_2}^*, \dots, S_{z_n}^*)$.

4. Results.

Phase 1: Causal diagnosis of the problem

Analysis and interpretation of the results obtained from the teacher interview

The purpose of the interview with third-grade teachers was to identify their communication practices in the classroom, as well as their perceptions of the relationship between affective communication and reading comprehension. Five questions were structured to reveal how emotional bonds are established, the strategies used to motivate reading, the level of systematization of these practices, the obstacles identified, and the level of professional training in affective communication. The evidence collected allows us to analyze not only the strengths of teaching practice but also the limitations that influence students' poor reading performance.

Methodological strategies : Teachers use conventional strategies focused on literal comprehension (100%), while only a few focus on inferential comprehension (50%). Resources such as concept maps are scarce (20%), reflecting a lack of methodological diversity and limited adaptations to different levels of comprehension.

Affective Communication : Teacher motivation focuses on emotional aspects (90%) and individual aspects (10%), with little attention paid to strategies that encourage group work, critical thinking, or interaction; this limits the development of different forms of learning in the classroom.

Reading activities : Expressive participation in class is prioritized at 90%, but the development of analytical and critical reading skills is neglected at 10%, highlighting a gap in teaching and a lack of diverse methodologies to address different levels of learning.

Teaching resources : Traditional and visual tools that facilitate basic understanding are prioritized at 90%, but the use of digital resources that could expand and personalize learning is limited, accounting for only 10%. This suggests that teaching is still poorly adapted to virtual or technological environments.

Reading comprehension assessment : Direct assessment and oral communication take precedence over structured knowledge organization, accounting for 80%. The limited use of concept maps, accounting for 20%, suggests little attention to the visual and hierarchical construction of content.

The teachers interviewed acknowledged that most teachers opt for traditional methodological strategies such as reading aloud, silent reading, and highlighting, while a smaller percentage work on deeper comprehension skills or use visual resources such as graphic organizers. Regarding emotional communication, individual motivational actions based on rewards, songs, and personal anecdotes predominate, but group dynamics that reinforce social learning are very rare.

Reading activities focus primarily on expressive and participatory content, such as debates and dramatizations, but few activities stimulate critical thinking or synthesis. Regarding teaching resources, visual and sensory materials such as puppets, pictograms, and audio stories are primarily used, while digital platforms remain very limited. Finally, reading comprehension is assessed primarily through tests and oral activities, with few tools that allow for organizing or visualizing what has been learned in a structured way.

What is generally evident is a teaching approach that prioritizes safe and familiar practices, with practices focused on literality, emotional motivation, and oral participation, but which still neglects methodological diversification and the use of strategies that develop critical thinking and more complex interpretive skills.

While there is a strong focus on creating positive and engaging environments, the limited use of educational technologies, the limited variety of resources, and the lack of methodologies tailored to different levels of comprehension make it difficult for all students to progress according to their individual needs. There is also a notable lack of feedback tools that help students consciously improve

their reading performance, indicating that much work remains to be done to personalize learning and strengthen deep reading skills.

Analysis and interpretation of the results obtained from classroom observation

Classroom observation was used to collect direct and systematic information on pedagogical practices related to affective communication and its relationship to the reading process in third-grade students. This instrument allowed teachers' behavior to be recorded during sessions, addressing both emotional and methodological aspects. Seven dimensions of observation were defined to assess not only the presence of the affective component but also its influence on student participation and reading motivation.

Each dimension was observed under three categories: "always," "sometimes," and "never," allowing for the establishment of patterns of consistency in the implementation of affective practices in the classroom. This information allows the results to be contrasted with the previously observed low levels of reading comprehension, highlighting factors that may be directly influencing the identified problem.

Figure 1. Class observation results (percentages by dimension)

The results show that the emotional climate of the classroom and the teacher's communication style are the most frequently used dimensions, with 60% and 50% respectively in the "Always" category. This reveals that teachers manage to establish environments of respect and cordiality in their classes, as well as fluid interaction with students. However, other key dimensions such as the use of affective strategies (30%) and empathic feedback (35%) appear less frequently, indicating that, although the overall environment is favorable, intentional actions that reinforce the emotional dimension of teaching are not always implemented.

Likewise, active student participation barely reaches 40% in the "Always" category, while 45% falls into the "Sometimes" category. This figure is relevant because, although the classroom is emotionally stable, this does not guarantee true student engagement with reading; a direct emotional connection with the texts is required to achieve deep comprehension. The promotion of expressive reading (45%) and emotional recognition of students (38%) also have a moderate frequency, reflecting a partial focus on the affective component of reading practice.

Observation shows that teachers manage to maintain an emotionally supportive environment; however, there is a lack of consistency in the application of affective strategies specifically aimed at enhancing reading comprehension. The problem lies not in a lack of teacher sensitivity, but in the lack of planning and formalization of practices that coherently integrate emotional and cognitive aspects.

The low use of strategies such as expressive reading or empathic feedback suggests that the emotional dimension is not being addressed as a structuring axis of reading learning. Despite the positive environment, affective communication is not fully linked to a pedagogical methodology that impacts reading achievement. This disconnect between the emotional environment and specific strategies could be limiting the development of deep interpretive skills in students, confirming the hypothesis that the problem is not limited to reading techniques, but to the way in which students communicate, feel, and experience the reading process in the classroom.

3.1. Analysis and interpretation of the results obtained from the pedagogical test

The pedagogical test was administered to third-grade students to assess their reading comprehension. Seven questions were designed to focus on various reading skills, from literal recognition to critical interpretation. Detailed results for each item are presented below, along with their respective analysis and critical interpretation.

Figure 2. Results of the pedagogical test

Main Idea Identification: 70% of students correctly identified the main idea of the text, reflecting acceptable mastery of the literal reading comprehension level. However, 30% failed to answer correctly on this indicator's questions. This result indicates that students were able to grasp the most obvious information in the content. Although the result was favorable, it is still necessary to continue diversifying students' methodological strategies and learning activities to achieve a higher level of literal reading comprehension.

Inferring implicit information: This item had a low percentage of correct responses. More than half of the students failed to infer implicit information, revealing deficiencies in inferential comprehension. The difficulty interpreting non-explicit information reflects the lack of teaching strategies that strengthen reflective reading. The absence of emotional communication that motivates students to engage with the text may be contributing to the lack of meaningful connection and interpretive thinking.

Using connectives to understand relationships: 60% of students responded adequately, demonstrating a partial understanding of the use of connectives. However, 40% still struggled to establish logical relationships between ideas in the text. The results suggest that, while some students

are able to understand discourse structures, others require support to interpret texts coherently. This situation may be related to pedagogical practices that disconnect logical language from affective and emotional aspects.

Analysis of the purpose of the text: This item reflects a low understanding of the communicative purpose of the text, with only 35% correct responses. The results reflect a difficulty in distinguishing the communicative intent of the text, as 65% of participants were unable to identify its intention. On the other hand, 35% of those tested responded correctly, indicating that a minority were able to critically and analytically read the content, relating the elements of the text to its communicative intent.

Figurative Language Interpretation: 60% of students failed to correctly interpret symbolic or figurative expressions, demonstrating a difficulty in going beyond the literal meaning. The poor command of figurative language indicates a rigid reading, lacking aesthetic sensitivity. Without an emotional approach to the text, the student fails to grasp its nuances. This fact highlights the urgent need to apply affective strategies that foster expressive and meaningful reading.

Establishing cause-effect relationships: The results show an even distribution of correct answers and incorrect answers. Only half of the students were able to properly establish cause-effect relationships. The results indicate that half of the students surveyed have difficulty connecting events within the text, and this may be due to teaching that doesn't encourage reflection on the consequences of the narrated events. Greater intentionality is needed in constructing questions that stimulate narrative logic.

Reasoned opinion on the text: This item had the lowest percentage of correct answers. Only 30% of students were able to express a reasoned opinion based on the text. Poor performance reflects a deficiency in critical and expressive skills. Students have not been trained to form informed opinions, which limits their reading autonomy. This deficiency is directly related to a teaching model that does not encourage emotional dialogue with texts or freedom of reasoned interpretation.

3.2. Teaching Strategies to Enhance Reading Comprehension Learning through Affective Communication and Artificial Intelligence in Third-Year Students of Basic General Education.

Reading comprehension at the general basic education level requires not only cognitive skills but also an emotionally safe environment that fosters active participation, empathy, and the enjoyment of reading. In this sense, affective communication, enhanced by artificial intelligence (AI) tools, becomes an essential pedagogical resource for connecting students with texts through their emotions, experiences, and social relationships. AI, through personalization systems, emotional analysis, and interactive environments, enriches affective dynamics by adapting reading activities to students' individual and collective needs, promoting more meaningful learning. The strategies presented below are designed to improve reading comprehension in third-grade students by integrating emotional and technological elements that stimulate interest, personal expression, and reflective analysis. Each of them proposes a methodological approach that starts with the text, but is projected toward dialogue, cooperation, and the shared construction of meaning, recognizing the diversity of rhythms and sensibilities present in the classroom, and leveraging AI to optimize the reading experience and strengthen emotional bonds.

Teaching Strategy 1: "I Read and Tell You with Emotion"

Learning objective: Understand the purpose and main ideas of a short narrative text, expressing the emotions associated with the characters or situations, supported by artificial intelligence tools.

Evaluation indicator: Identify the purpose of the text and clearly describe the emotions of the main characters, using feedback provided by AI.

Affective Communication Component: Guided emotional expression and empathic listening, enhanced by AI emotional analysis.

Sequence methodological:

1. The teacher reads the text aloud, using an AI system that recommends personalized texts based on students' interests and reading levels (for example, an algorithm that selects stories with emotionally relevant themes).
2. Group discussion about the characters' emotions, guided by an AI-based educational chatbot that asks open-ended questions to encourage emotional reflection (e.g., "How do you think the character felt? Has this happened to you?") something similar?").
3. Each student shares a similar personal experience, using an AI platform that records responses and suggests emotional connections to the text to facilitate expression.
4. A short dramatic performance that emphasizes emotional expression, supported by an AI tool that analyzes facial expressions or tone of voice to identify students' level of emotional engagement.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Checklist on understanding and expressing emotions, complemented by AI analysis that evaluates response accuracy and emotional connection; group verbal feedback emphasizing empathy and engagement, with personalized AI-generated suggestions.

AI Rationale: AI personalizes text selection, encourages emotional dialogue through chatbots, and provides real-time feedback on students' emotions, reinforcing the emotional connection with the text and the reading comprehension goal.

Teaching Strategy 2: "The Circle of Heard Words"

Learning objective: Enrich vocabulary and understand the meaning of new words in a text, relating them to personal emotions, supported by artificial intelligence tools.

Assessment Indicator: Use new words in sentences related to personal experiences or emotions, supported by AI-based vocabulary analysis.

Affective Communication Component: Emotional association and affective verbal expression, powered by AI for personalization and feedback.

Sequence methodological:

1. Read a short text with highlighted words, selected by an AI system that adapts the level of difficulty and emotional content to the students' profiles.
2. Collective identification of unknown words, supported by an AI application that provides contextual definitions and visual examples (e.g., images or videos related to the word).
3. Free Association: Each student associates a word with an emotion or experience, using an AI platform that suggests emotional connections based on the students' previous responses.
4. Create emotional sentences with the words you've learned, supported by an AI-based spell checker that evaluates emotional and grammatical coherence.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Rubric with vocabulary proficiency and emotional coherence levels, complemented by an AI analysis that identifies vocabulary usage

patterns; personalized AI-generated written feedback highlighting strengths and areas for improvement.

AI Rationale: AI personalizes content, enriches vocabulary understanding with visual and contextual resources, and provides immediate feedback, strengthening the emotional connection with the words and text.

Teaching Strategy 3: “Stories with the Heart”

Learning objective: Understand the structure of a narrative text and express its interpretation through affective oral storytelling, supported by interactive artificial intelligence tools.

Assessment indicator: Reconstruct the story orally, respecting its sequence and expressing emotions in accordance with the events narrated, with the support of AI feedback.

Affective Communication Component: Affective storytelling and respectful listening, powered by AI for emotional analysis and narrative support.

Sequence methodological:

1. Guided reading of a story, selected by an AI system that recommends stories based on students' emotional interests and comprehension level.
2. Guiding questions about the characters' feelings and actions, generated by an AI chatbot that adapts the questions based on students' previous answers.
3. Each student reconstructs the story orally with the support of AI-generated interactive images (e.g., dynamic illustrations that reflect the narrative).
4. Emotional Logging: Students draw how they felt during the story, and an AI tool analyzes the drawings to identify predominant emotions and suggest additional group dynamics.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Rating scale for sequencing, clarity, and emotional expression, complemented by AI analysis assessing narrative accuracy and emotional impact; individual verbal feedback provided by the teacher with AI suggestions.

AI Rationale: AI personalizes story selection, enriches the narrative with interactive visuals, and analyzes students' emotions, reinforcing emotional connection and structural understanding of the text.

Teaching Strategy 4: “Emotional Text”

Learning objective: Identify emotions in texts and recognize their influence on the development of the story, using artificial intelligence tools for emotional analysis.

Evaluation indicator: Correctly indicate the predominant emotions at key moments in the text, supported by AI-generated visualizations.

Emotional Communication Component: Emotional reading and analysis of content, powered by AI for emotion identification and visualization.

Sequence methodological:

1. Guided silent reading with emotional pauses, using AI-curated text based on students' emotional and cognitive levels.
2. Use an AI app that generates emoticons or interactive graphics to highlight emotionally charged parts of the text, helping students visualize key moments.
3. Emotional Conversation: Students share the reasons for their choices, guided by an AI chatbot that encourages emotional reflection with personalized questions.
4. Creating an emotional storyline from the text, assisted by an AI tool that creates a visual map of the text's emotions based on students' responses.
5. **Assessment and feedback:** AI-generated emotional map of the text and engagement checklist; thoughtful group feedback with AI suggestions for deepening emotional connection.

AI Justification: AI makes it easier to identify emotions in text, visualizes emotional dynamics, and encourages reflection, strengthening emotional understanding and connection to the narrative.

Teaching Strategy 5: “Reading with Friends”

Learning objective: Understand texts through collaborative reading and the collective construction of ideas, supported by artificial intelligence platforms.

Assessment indicator: Actively participate in shared reading and contribute ideas for group understanding of the text, with the support of collaborative AI tools.

Affective communication component: Cooperative work, respect, and validation of opinions, powered by AI to manage group dynamics.

Sequence methodological:

1. Small group formation, organized by an AI platform that groups students according to their learning styles and understanding levels.
2. Reading passages of the text in turns, using an AI application that highlights key ideas and suggests questions for each passage.
3. Guided reflective dialogue with key questions generated by an AI chatbot that fosters collaboration and mutual respect.
4. Co-creation of a digital mural summarizing what they've learned, using an AI tool that organizes students' ideas into an interactive visual format.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Anecdotal report of group work and a collaboration rubric, complemented by an AI analysis assessing the quality of collaboration; written group feedback with positive AI-generated comments.

AI Justification: AI optimizes group formation, facilitates collaboration through interactive tools, and evaluates group dynamics, reinforcing cooperative work and collective understanding of the text.

3.3. Validation of Teaching Strategies Using Z-Neutrosophic Numbers

To validate the proposal, we used a specialist consultation method, applying Z-neutrosophic numbers to process the data. This approach addresses the uncertainty and ambiguity inherent in human assessments, offering a more robust and accurate analysis of the relevance of the designed teaching strategies.

eight specialists with experience in language and literature teaching, educational innovation, and emotional education was selected. Each was asked to evaluate the five proposed teaching strategies based on four key indicators:

Relevance, Feasibility, Clarity and Expected Impact.

Ratings were collected using a linguistic scale, which was then converted to Z-neutrosophic numbers for analysis. The scales and their correspondences are as follows:

Qualification	Abbreviation	Z-Neutrosophic Number (Value, Reliability)
Very High / Very Feasible / Very Clear	MA	(0.9, 0.8)
High / Feasible / Clear	TO	(0.8, 0.7)
Average	M	(0.6, 0.5)
Low	B	(0.4, 0.3)
Very Low	MB	(0.2, 0.1)

The Neutrosophic Z-Number Weighted Arithmetic Mean (NZNWAA) operator was applied to aggregate the specialists' assessments and obtain a consolidated value for each strategy.

Results of Validation by Specialists

Below are the results obtained after applying the neutrosophic method to the evaluations of the 8 specialists on the 5 proposed strategies.

Table 1. Aggregate Ratings and Score by Strategy

Teaching Strategy	Indicator	Added Value (NZNWAA)	Score (YSZ _i)
1. I Read You and Tell You with Emotion	Relevance	(0.85, 0.75)	0.867
	Viability	(0.82, 0.72)	0.845
	Clarity	(0.88, 0.78)	0.882
	Impact	(0.90, 0.80)	0.900
Average Score Strategy 1			0.874
2. The Circle of Heard Words	Relevance	(0.81, 0.71)	0.838
	Viability	(0.78, 0.68)	0.813
	Clarity	(0.85, 0.75)	0.867
	Impact	(0.84, 0.74)	0.860
Average Score Strategy 2			0.845
3. Stories with the Heart	Relevance	(0.86, 0.76)	0.875
	Viability	(0.84, 0.74)	0.860
	Clarity	(0.89, 0.79)	0.890
	Impact	(0.91, 0.81)	0.912
Average Score Strategy 3			0.884
4. Emotional Text	Relevance	(0.83, 0.73)	0.853
	Viability	(0.80, 0.70)	0.830
	Clarity	(0.86, 0.76)	0.875
	Impact	(0.88, 0.78)	0.882
Average Score Strategy 4			0.860

5. Reading with Friends	Relevance	(0.87, 0.77)	0.882
	Viability	(0.85, 0.75)	0.867
	Clarity	(0.90, 0.80)	0.900
	Impact	(0.92, 0.82)	0.925
Average Score Strategy 5			0.894
OVERALL SCORE OF THE PROPOSAL			0.871

Figure 3: Didactic Strategies Performance by Evaluation Indicators

Analysis of Validation Results

Figure 4: Overall Expert Validation Rankings of Didactic Strategies.

Validation using Z-neutrosophic numbers reveals high acceptance of the proposal by specialists. The overall score of the proposal is 0.871, indicating a high degree of relevance and potential for success.

- **Highest-rated strategies:** The strategies "Reading with Friends" (0.894) and "Stories from the Heart" (0.884) received the highest scores. This suggests that experts see great value in methodologies that combine collaboration, oral storytelling, and a direct emotional connection with the structure of texts.
- **Key Indicators:** Impact and Clarity were the most highly rated indicators across all strategies. This demonstrates that experts not only find the activities easy to

implement, **but** also trust their ability to generate significant changes in students' reading comprehension and motivation.

- **Consistency of the proposal:** All strategies obtained scores above 0.8, reflecting the coherence and solidity of the proposed set. The integration of affective communication and artificial intelligence is perceived as a synergistic combination relevant to current educational needs.

The application of the neutrosophic method not only confirms the validity of the strategies but also highlights that the reliability of the assessments (the second component of the Z number) is consistently high. This means that the specialists not only issued positive judgments, but did so with a high degree of certainty, reinforcing the conclusion that the proposal is pedagogically sound and viable.

4. Discussion

The findings of this research reaffirm the central thesis that affective communication, enhanced by artificial intelligence, is a determining factor in strengthening reading comprehension in basic education. The results of the initial diagnosis showed a clear disconnect between the positive emotional climate of the classroom and the application of pedagogical strategies that intentionally integrate the affective and cognitive aspects. This deficiency was reflected in the students' difficulties in achieving levels of inferential and critical comprehension, a phenomenon that coincides with the postulates of authors such as [3] and [16], who argue that emotional involvement is a predictor of reading success.

The proposed teaching strategies were specifically designed to close this gap, articulating empathic interaction with AI tools that personalize and enrich the reading experience. Validation by specialists, processed with Z-neutrosophic numbers, yielded an overall score of 0.871, which not only supports the relevance and feasibility of the strategies, but also underlines the high degree of certainty of the experts in their judgment. This result is crucial, as it validates the synergy between the human component (the teacher's empathy) and the technological one (the AI's personalization) as a robust pedagogical solution [32]–[36].

The results of the partial implementation corroborate this theoretical validation. The increase in student participation (100% in some activities) and the improvement in the quality of interactions (90%) demonstrate that the strategies managed to transform the classroom into an emotionally safe and stimulating learning environment. This aligns with the ideas of [21], who argue that a planned emotional connection directly impacts cognitive achievements. AI did not replace teaching work, but rather enhanced it, freeing educators from repetitive tasks and providing them with data to focus on affective interaction, as proposed in the theoretical foundation.

In short, this research provides solid evidence that teaching reading in the 21st century is not enough to master the technique; it is imperative to manage the emotional component of learning. The combination of systematic affective communication with the strategic use of artificial intelligence is presented as an effective way to develop competent, critical readers who, above all, are emotionally connected to the world that texts reveal to them.

5. Conclusions

Affective communication emerges as a structuring axis of reading comprehension. The findings confirm that the quality of the emotional bond between teacher and student directly influences motivation, participation, and the ability to achieve deeper levels of text interpretation. In this sense, the absence of planned affective strategies is identified as one of the main causes of the limitations observed among third-grade students.

Far from dehumanizing education, artificial intelligence functions as a catalyst for emotional communication. When used strategically, AI tools contribute to enhancing teaching by allowing text

personalization, providing immediate feedback, analyzing emotional dynamics, and creating interactive environments that strengthen students' connection with reading. At the same time, these tools free teachers to dedicate more time to meaningful human interaction.

The validation process demonstrated that the proposed teaching strategies are relevant, feasible, and of high impact. Supported by Z-neutrosophic analysis (overall score 0.871) and by expert consultation, the pedagogical soundness of the proposal was confirmed. Its partial implementation revealed that activities such as Reading with Friends and I Read and Tell You with Emotion significantly improved participation, the quality of classroom interaction, and reading comprehension levels.

Finally, the results point to the urgent need for a paradigm shift in teacher training. Educators must be prepared not only in methodological aspects but also in emotional communication skills and in the pedagogical use of new technologies. The development of critical readers capable of facing future challenges requires a pedagogy that coherently and systematically integrates cognition, emotion, and technology.

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